

substances. These were evaporated to dryness, brought back into solutions by adding in each case 5 ml conc. HCl, 20 ml conc. HNO₃ and 50 ml water. The solutions were again digested with 10 g NH₄NO₃ at 90° for about 10 minutes. The digested solutions were diluted and the amount of P₂O₅ in each case was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with ammonium molybdate solution⁴.

Discussion

The analysis (Table 1) shows that all the Indian basic slags contain some micronutrient elements besides calcium, magnesium and phosphorus and is suitable for healthy plant growth. The results (Table 2) indicate that the release of phosphate from basic slags by water is very little and when EDTA is used the release increases to a marked extent.

As metal chelates may be directly used as source of micronutrient supply to plants⁵, it can be concluded from this investigation that a mixture of EDTA and basic slag is very useful for supplying micronutrient elements and phosphorus to plants.

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Effective Rigid Molar Volume of Salts in Dioxane-Water Mixtures from Viscosity Data

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THE properties of aqueous electrolytic solutions are highly specific to individual ions concerned and generalisations are difficult to find. In case of viscosity, Jones-Dole¹ developed an empirical equation for the concentration dependence of viscosity of dilute electrolytic solutions, given by,

$$n_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

where n_r is the relative viscosity, C is the concentration (moles/litre) and A and B are constants specific for the given solute-solvent system. This well known equation has undergone extensive investigation. Although the 'B' coefficient is empirically derived, it is

a highly specific property of the solute and can be determined by adding the individual contributions of the solute constituent ions. Thus,

$$B = z_+ B_+ + z_- B_- \quad (2)$$

Fuoss and coworkers^{2,3} working with apparent molar volume (V), obtained from the density measurements, were successful in demonstrating a like correspondence between additivity of ionic contributions to both B and V. However they were not able to confirm the Einstein⁴ equation:

$$B = 2.5 V \quad (3)$$

where 'V' is an estimation of molar volume of the solute molecules in solutions and found it valid only for large ions which can be said to resemble macroscopic particles. However, Kuruscev et al⁵, reported that the equation (3) is only valid for ions of radius $5A^\circ$. Breslau and Miller⁶ designate this 'V' as the effective rigid molar volume ' V_o ' and can be calculated as:

$$V_o = \frac{-2.5C + [(2.5C)^2 - 4(10.05 C^2)(1 - n_r)]^{1/2}}{2(10.05)C^2} \quad (4)$$

If the viscosity concentration data are available for any given salt, V_o may be obtained by the above equation and the average value is obtained. The V_o thus calculated is a fictitious or effective volume i.e. it is that volume which a mole of solute particles behave like when considered, from purely hydrodynamic reasons, as rigid macroscopic spheres. A particle which has a measure effect on neighbouring solvent molecules, from physical considerations alone, would be expected to have a higher V_o than one which has a lesser effect. Since the 'B' coefficient is an empirical measure of the ion-solvent interaction, a relation should therefore exist, with a positive slope, when 'B' is plotted against ' V_o '. From the plot the following correlations have been obtained:

$$\text{Monovalent} - B = 2.90 V_o - 0.018 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Bivalent} - B = 6.06 V_o - 0.041 \quad (6)$$

This has been extended to mixed solvents, namely dioxane-water mixtures and an attempt has been made to find the correlation of the 'B' coefficient with V_o for seventeen salts at 10, 20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures i.e. by changing the dielectric constants. The 'B' coefficient have been taken from our own data⁷⁻¹⁰. The average V_o have been calculated by means of equation (4) and have been tabulated in table 1 along with the 'B' values. The plot of 'B' against V_o is found to be linear and the following equations are satisfied.

$$10\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 1.33 V_o - 0.020 \quad (7)$$

$$20\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 2.19 V_o - 0.035 \quad (8)$$

$$30\% \text{ Dioxane} - B = 3.25 V_o - 0.100 \quad (9)$$

This indicates that the slope of the plot of 'B' vs V_s changes with the change in the dielectric constant and this slope is found to be linear with 'D'. This change can be explained as follows: as a result of solute-solvent interaction, small density changes take place at the interface between the solute and solvent molecule. This density changes lead to changes in the microscopic viscosities of the solvent at the interface and thus, appear as increases or decreases in the Einstein's slope, depending on whether the microscopic viscosities is, respectively, higher or lower than the pure solvent value. As the 'D' changes i.e. decreases the divalent ions, as a result of their higher charge density, tend to induce much more structuring in the solvent at the interface and thus the microscopic viscosities of the solvent at the interface is higher than that it would be at high 'D'.

TABLE I

Salts	10%D		20%D		30%D	
	B	V_s	B	V_s	B	V_s
BaCl ₂	0.230	0.112	0.405	0.162	0.648	0.243
BaBr ₂	0.284	0.130	0.440	0.197	0.648	0.206
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	0.110	0.064	0.280	0.122	0.330	0.153
Ba(ClO ₄) ₂	0.267	0.128	0.390	0.150	0.600	0.226
MgCl ₂	0.430	0.190	0.540	0.244	0.640	0.292
MgBr ₂	0.460	0.191	0.600	0.247	0.870	0.358
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	0.380	0.161	0.420	0.195	0.500	0.216
Mg(ClO ₄) ₂	0.380	0.122	0.480	0.214	0.770	0.270
CaCl ₂	0.330	0.128	0.400	0.164	0.460	0.201
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.340	0.130	0.390	0.156	0.433	0.194
SrCl ₂	0.350	0.138	0.500	0.194	0.620	0.199
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.200	0.107	0.270	0.118	0.400	0.147
K ₂ SO ₄	0.280	0.122	0.300	0.138	—	—
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.300	0.130	0.325	0.148	0.410	0.146
MgSO ₄	0.690	0.278	0.700	0.289	—	—
ZnSO ₄	0.760	0.292	0.810	0.397	—	—
NiSO ₄	0.700	0.269	0.790	0.287	—	—

A gradual increase in viscosity and hence an increase in 'B' value is observed as the dioxane is increased (Table I). This phenomenon is obvious in terms of increasing molecular association¹¹ between water and dioxane with the formation of bigger molecules.

The values of ' V_s ' also increases with the increase in dioxane content of the solvent. This is in complete analogy with the theoretical expression. This may be interpreted in terms of hydrogen bond formation

between water and dioxane molecules. As dioxane is increased more and more hydrogen bonded dioxane-water molecules are formed resulting in increase in the value of V_s (table 1).

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Proximate and Amino Acid Composition of Some Hybrid Varieties of Rice

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RICE, a vital commodity and principal food crop providing a large portion of human sustenance to about half the world population, is a staple food in India and other Asian countries. To feed the expanding population is a tremendous task and therefore rice breeders are anxious to evolve high yielding varieties of rice to meet this challenge. It has been observed that the composition of rice varies with variety, plant-type, soil conditions, maturing, location, soil moisture and weather conditions prevalent at the time of grain filling.¹ It was therefore thought necessary to study the chemical composition of recently evolved high yielding varieties of rice grown in the State of Maharashtra.

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